

Catalytic Oxidation of Carbon Monoxide over Perovskite-type Catalysts

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Catalytic oxidation of carbon monoxide over the perovskite-type mixed catalysts $\text{La}_{(1+x)/2}\text{Sr}_{(1-x)/2}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_{3-\lambda}$ ($0.1 \leq x \leq 0.9$) has been investigated. Activity testing results show that the catalysts in the range $x = 0.1-0.4$ are of high activity for CO oxidation, especially, the catalyst of $x = 0.4$ can make CO to oxidize completely below 170° and is regarded as the optimum catalyst for CO oxidation. Studies also suggest that oxidizing atmosphere favors CO oxidation over perovskite catalyst, the catalyst of $x = 0.4$ has higher resistance to sulfur dioxide poisoning at higher temperature. Studies on the active oxygen species by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and desorption of oxygen suggest that the important active oxygen species for CO oxidation is the surface-absorbed oxygen.

In perovskite type oxides represented by ABO_3 , the replacement of A and/or B site cations by other metal cations often brings about the formation of oxygen vacancies and the change in the oxidation state of the B site cation, which are related to the high catalytic activity for CO oxidation and so have become an area of very active investigation in the catalytic field¹, especially those which contain Co or Mn in B site present very high catalytic activity and promise to be alternative to noble metals (Pd and Pt) as the exhaust combustion catalysts. However, the study on the system in which A site and B site are substituted with lower valence metal cations simultaneously and with the component model $\text{La}_{(1+x)/2}\text{Sr}_{(1-x)/2}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_{3-\lambda}$ has not been reported to date. In this study, we present the perovskite-type catalysts $\text{La}_{(1+x)/2}\text{Sr}_{(1-x)/2}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_{3-\lambda}$ ($0.1 \leq x \leq 0.9$) and their activity for CO oxidation over the studied catalysts.

Results and Discussion

Activity of $\text{La}_{(1+x)/2}\text{Sr}_{(1-x)/2}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_{3-\lambda}$ for CO oxidation: Fig. 1 shows the conversion of CO over the catalysts

Fig. 1. CO oxidation activity of $\text{La}_{(1+x)/2}\text{Sr}_{(1-x)/2}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_{3-\lambda}$ at different temperatures: (a) 100° , (b) 130° , (c) 150° , (d) 160° and (e) 180° .

at different temperatures. At temperature below 150° , four regions of activity can be discerned as a result of increasing x : (a) increase of activity for a small substitution up to $x = 0.2$, (b) fall in activity with further substitution up to $x = 0.3$, (c) a sharp increase in activity up to $x = 0.4$ and (d) fall in activity for $x \geq 0.4$. At temperature above 150° , two regions of activity can be discerned as a result of increasing x , that is, the activity increases with x and reaches the highest up to $x = 0.4$, then decreases with x . At 180° , the conversion of CO over the catalysts in the range $x = 0.1-0.4$ reaches 100%, which shows that the activity of these catalysts for CO oxidation is very high, especially, we can see, at different temperatures, the activity reaches the maximum up to $x = 0.4$. In addition, under the experiment conditions, the catalyst of $x = 0.4$ can make CO to oxidize completely below 170° , so the catalyst of $x = 0.4$ is regarded as the optimum catalyst for complete CO oxidation.

Fig. 2. Effect of the gas composition variation in the feed: (a) 4.48% CO + 16.30% O_2 + 79.22% N_2 and (b) 4.48% CO + 4.28% H_2 + 12.0% O_2 + 79.24% N_2 .

Effect of the composition variation in feed gases: It is reported² that the composition variation in the feed gas in-

fluences the efficiency of the perovskite catalysts for removal of exhaust emission, and the oxidizing mixture of feed gases favor CO and CH_x oxidation and the reducing mixture does NO_x reduction over perovskite catalyst. Here, taking La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-λ} an example, we investigated the effect of the gas composition variation in feed. Because our attention is focused on CO oxidation, the gas composition has been varied only in oxidizing atmosphere. As shown in Fig. 2, although there was the same concentration (v/v) of CO in the mixture gases in curve-a and curve-b, 4.28% H₂ was added to the mixture in curve-b, which resulted that the ratio of concentrations of the reducing components of the mixture to that of oxygen is increased from about 1 : 4 in curve-a to about 1 : 1 : 2 in curve-b. This means that the catalyst is in more oxidizing atmosphere in curve-a than in curve-b, as a result, higher CO conversion was observed in curve-a than in curve-b at the same temperature. The results confirm that oxidizing atmosphere favors CO oxidation over perovskite catalyst, in other words, the efficiency of perovskite catalyst for CO oxidation is higher in oxidizing conditions.

Fig. 3. Dependence of CO conversion on number of pulsing SO₂ at different temperatures : (1) 180° (2) 240° and (3) 345°.

Effect of sulphur dioxide : SO₂ poisoning is known to be important in the deactivation of solid catalysts, especially, base metal oxide catalysts are more susceptible to poisoning by sulfur³. Indeed, the deactivation of oxides when used in oxidation or reduction process and particularly as catalysts for exhaust gas purification, has been attributed to a large extent to sulfur dioxide⁴. Here, SO₂ poisoning effect was studied through pulsing SO₂ into the catalytical reactor bed which was used for oxidizing CO. As illustrated in Fig. 3, at lower temperature, CO conversion is influenced seriously and decreased rapidly with increasing number of pulsing SO₂. This result suggests that the catalyst is easily poisoned by SO₂ at lower temperature, and its resistance to SO₂ poisoning is enhanced with increasing temperature. From Fig. 3, it can be seen that the

catalyst has higher resistance to SO₂ poisoning at 345°. In fact, this temperature is not high for exhaust combustion, so for removal of CO from exhaust emission, the catalyst of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-λ} has high resistance to SO₂ poisoning.

The TGA curves (figures not shown) of the studied catalysts ($x = 0.1-0.6$) in the reducing conditions, show no apparent weight-loss for all the catalysts below 250°, but there appears three plateau due to the weight-loss of oxygen in the range 250–900°. This reflects that there exist three different types of oxygen in the catalysts, the first oxygen which lost weight below 450° is termed as the surface oxygen I, and the second in the range 450–700° is the surface oxygen II. As reported⁵, the crystal structure of perovskite is destroyed at about 800° in the reducing conditions, so the third at about 800° is termed as the bulk lattice oxygen. The oxygen reduced by hydrogen is inevitably attributed to active oxygen, on the reducing conditions; the more the surface oxygen reduced by hydrogen is the greater is the weight-loss, so the more there exists the surface oxygen in the catalysts.

Table I shows that the content of the surface oxygen changes with x , for the surface oxygen I with increasing x , its content increases gradually and reaches the maximum up to $x = 0.4$ and then decreases with x , so is the total content of the surface oxygen. This trend is similar to that of activity for CO oxidation, indicating that the activity for CO oxidation over the studied catalysts is related to the

TABLE I—RESULTS OF TGA FOR La_{(1+x)/2}Sr_{(1-x)/2}Co_{1-x}Cu_xO_{3-λ}

	x					
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
C _I (%)	4.60	4.70	5.66	6.10	5.80	4.32
C _{II} (%)	2.90	3.10	2.84	3.50	2.90	2.80
C _{I+II} (%)	7.50	7.80	8.50	9.60	8.70	7.12

C_I = content of surface oxygen I; C_{II} = content of surface oxygen II; C_{I+II} = total content of surface oxygen I and II.

surface oxygen, particularly, to the surface oxygen I. It is apparent that the more the surface oxygen I is the higher is the activity. So we suppose that surface oxygen I and II are

Fig. 4. XPS for O_{1s} level of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-λ} at (a) room temperature and (b) 450°.

the active oxygen species of the studied catalysts and the surface oxygen I has more important effect on CO oxidation.

O_{1s} XPS of $La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-\lambda}$: The electron binding energy of O_{1s} is about 530 eV for lattice oxygen, which is slightly higher than that for chemically adsorbed oxygen (532 eV)⁶. It can be seen in Fig. 4 that the relative intensity of the chemisorbed oxygen and the surface lattice oxygen is different at two temperature, at room temperature the intensity of the former is stronger than that of the latter, and at 450° the case reverses. The results suggest that the chemisorbed oxygen is absorbed in the surface of the catalyst and so it is not stable and very active at high temperature. Therefore we suppose that in TGA curves, the surface oxygen I is possibly attributed to the surface adsorbed oxygen, and surface oxygen II is the surface lattice oxygen.

Fig. 5. Curves of desorption of oxygen for $La_{(1+x)/2}Sr_{(1-x)/2}Co_{1-x}Cu_xO_{3-\lambda}$.

Desorption of oxygen: Fig. 5 shows the desorption of oxygen for $La_{(1+x)/2}Sr_{(1-x)/2}Co_{1-x}Cu_xO_{3-\lambda}$ in the range 0–850°. It can be seen that the catalysts show three desorption peaks: a (around 200°), b (in the range 300–600°) and c (at ~800°). Combining with the results given by TGA and O_{1s} XPS, we suppose that a is the surface adsorbed oxygen, b the surface lattice oxygen and c the bulk lattice oxygen. And as can be seen, the intensity of peak-a is similar for all catalysts, however, the intensity of peak-b increases with x progressively and reaches maximum up to $x = 0.4$, then decreases with x . This is consistent with that of the surface oxygen I in TGA curves, indicating that surface adsorbed

oxygen is the important active oxygen species for CO oxidation.

Conclusion: (i) The perovskite-type catalysts $La_{(1+x)/2}Sr_{(1-x)/2}Co_{1-x}Cu_xO_{3-\lambda}$ in the range $x = 0.1-0.4$ have very high catalytic activity for CO oxidation, especially, the catalyst of $x = 0.4$ can make CO to oxidize completely below 170° under the experimental conditions, $La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-\lambda}$ is therefore regarded as the optimum catalyst for carbon monoxide oxidation. (ii) Oxidizing atmosphere favors CO oxidation over perovskite catalyst and $La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}Co_{0.6}Cu_{0.4}O_{3-\lambda}$ has high resistance to SO_2 poisoning at higher temperature. (iii) Combining the results given by TGA, XPS and desorption of oxygen, we suppose that the surface adsorbed oxygen is the important active oxygen species for CO oxidation over the studied catalysts.

Experimental

Preparation of catalysts: A series of $La_{(1+x)/2}Sr_{(1-x)/2}Co_{1-x}Cu_xO_3$ ($0.1 \leq x \leq 0.9$) perovskites was prepared. $La(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Sr(NO_3)_2$ and $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ (A.R.) were mixed together in required proportions to give a concentrated solution to which was added sufficient citric acid (A.R.) such that the number of gram equivalents added was a little excess to that of the metal ions. With the rapid dehydration of the solution at low temperature, followed by decomposition at about 300° and calcination at 600° in air for 4 h after having been ground into fine powder and mixed evenly, the resultant samples were calcined at 850° in air for 4 h. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on Shimadzu XD-3A diffractometer operating at 35 kV with a working current of 10 mA using CuK_{α} radiation in combination with a nickel filter. The samples up to $x = 0.6$ preserve perovskite, for $x \geq 0.7$, in addition to the perovskite, La_2CuO_4 and CuO were formed.

Catalyst activity: Activity testing was operated under atmospheric pressure and carried out in a fixed-bed flow micro-reactor, consisting of a piece of stainless steel tube (3 mm id \times 350 mm) packed with catalysts (0.5000 g, 60–80 mesh) and diluted by an excess of quartz sand. The temperature of the catalyst bed was measured by a chromel-copel thermocouple inserted coaxially in the reactor. Before each run, catalysts were pretreated in the reactor for 1 h at 600° in air. A mixture of the reactant gases (5.43% CO, 19.23% O_2 and 75.34% N_2) was passed through the reactor at a flow rate of 75 ml min^{-1} at preset temperature. For SO_2 poisoning test, 3.68% CO, 3.28% H_2 , 16.84% O_2 and 76.35% N_2 were contained in the feed gases and Ar was carrier gas, 1.3% SO_2 contained in N_2 was pulsed every 2 min. To examine the effect of composition variation in feed gases, one kind of mixture of gases containing 4.48% CO, 16.30% O_2 and 79.22% N_2 and the other containing 4.48% CO, 4.28% H_2 , 12.0% O_2 and 79.24% N_2 were used. Ar was used as carrier gas. The inlet and outlet gases were analyzed by gas chromatography (molecular sieve 5A, 60–80 mesh) with a thermoconductive detector (TCD) using hydrogen as a carrier gas. A

blank experiment using quartz chips in place of the catalyst showed no carbon monoxide conversion under the experimental conditions. The activity was presented by the apparent conversion of CO oxidation.

Thermogravimetric analysis : TGA for the catalysts was carried out with a Dupont 1090 apparatus under the following conditions : a flow of 10% H₂ + 90% N₂ at a rate of 50 ml min⁻¹, heating rate of 10° min⁻¹, in the temperature range 100–1000°.

Desorption of oxygen : Desorption of oxygen was carried out with a flow system using helium (purity 99.99%) as a carrier gas at atmospheric pressure. Prior to each run, the sample (0.1500 g) packed in the quartz-tube inserted in the PYR-2A pyrolysis furnace was treated in a He-stream for 1 h at 800° to clean the surface of the catalyst, followed by O₂ substitution for He and kept for 1 h at 800°, then cooled to room temperature in the O₂ stream, He stream was substituted for the O₂ stream at room temperature to scavenge the excess of oxygen in the surface of the catalyst, finally, the temperature of the sample was raised at the average rate of 130° min⁻¹ to 850° and the desorbed oxygen was monitored by TCD. The process and data were controlled by use of CR-3A microcomputer.

X-Ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) of O_{1s} : O_{1s} XPS was obtained with a Φ550 spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer) with MgKα (1253.6 eV) as the X-ray source (vacuum

chamber pressure 1 × 10⁻⁸ Pa). Before run, the sample was heated at 600° for 1 h, then cooled rapidly. Spectra were recorded for O_{1s} emission of the sample with *x* = 0.4 at room temperature and at 450° heating for 1 h. The binding energies were corrected by use of the value of 284.6 eV for the C_{1s} level resulting from the contaminated carbon.

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